

New Beginnings for IHRJ: Foraying into its Fourth Year of Publication...

IHRJ Editorial Team

Dear readers and authors,

Greetings from International Healthcare Research Journal (IHRJ)!

It is our pleasure to present the **Volume 4, Issue 1 (April 2020)** of IHRJ. The editorial team is extremely grateful to the contributors as without their efforts, it would have not come so far. IHRJ has always ventured to publish quality manuscripts in the all fields of healthcare. The success of IHRJ has motivated the editorial team to continue with the hard work and produce effective results. The authors have been the driving force in establishing it as a flourishing journal. There has been an immense response from readers which has taken IHRJ to its fourth year of existence due to which there are increased number of citations for various articles in the journal.

Last but not the least, we would again like to thank all the team members of IHRJ who have put their constant effort making the journal a grand achievement and wish luck for the future endeavours. We shall strive our best to make the journal one of the best platforms for aspiring authors.

It has been our earnest endeavour to provide assistance to our authors in any manner and as many times possible.

Stay safe! Stay healthy! As all of you are aware of the current scenario of COVID-19, we wish you and your family best of health in these testing times.

With Thanks and Regards,
Editorial Team

International Healthcare Research Journal (IHRJ).